

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

INTERNATIONAL PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Umarov A.A. – First Vice-Rector for Academic Affairs, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. – Professor, Head of Department, UWED

Rasulov A. S. – Professor, UWED

Bakoev M. T. – Academic Director of the Tashkent Branch of MGIMO.

Program Committee Members:

Formanov Sh. K. – Academician, AS of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Uzbekistan)

Aripov M. M. – Professor, NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Shadimetov Kh. M. – Professor, Tashkent State Technical University

Aloev R. – Professor, NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Khayotov A. R. – Professor, Institute of Mathematics, Academy of Sciences (Uzbekistan)

Khudoyberganov M. O. – Professor, NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Sharipov O. Sh. – NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Eshkuvvatov Z. K. – Professor, National Research University TIAME (Uzbekistan)

Kobulov A. V. – Professor, NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Mascagni M. – Professor, Florida State University (USA)

Li Y. – Professor, Old Dominion University (USA)

Gemma M. – Professor, Vice President of Waseda University (Japan)

Nishimura Shoji – Professor, Dean of Waseda University (Japan)

Hwang C. O. – Professor, Gwangju Institute of Science and Technology (Korea)

Seitov A. Zh. – Professor, UWED (Uzbekistan)

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Djalalov M.M. – Vice-Rector for Digital Transformation and Economy, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. – Head of the Department of System Analysis and Mathematical Modelling, UWED

Bakoev M. T. – Academic Director of the Tashkent Branch of MGIMO

Organizing Committee Members:

Abdullaev E.E. (Dean, UWED, Uzbekistan)

Dalabaev U. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova M. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Seitov A. Zh. UWED, Uzbekistan)

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT

Umarova Sh.G. (Head of the Secretariat), Buriev A., Kasimova N.J., Maraimova K. Sh., Khasanova D.R.,
Yarashev I., Solaeva M., Mustafakulova A. Kh., Akabirkhodjaeva D.R.

International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Discrete model of interaction between two populations

Ganikhodjaev, Nasir

V.I. Romanovskiy Institute of Mathematics, Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences, Tashkent
nasirgani@yandex.ru

Keywords: Interaction between two populations, Friedman's model, Discrete model.

We consider a model features interactions of several strategically distinct populations, so as to represent economic relationships between buyers and sellers, officials and applicants, or between residents in different jurisdictions, etc.

Discrete Friedman's model

In [1] the author provided the following model of interaction between two populations. It is considered a stylized interaction between two populations, called "buyers" and "sellers". Each seller has available two possible actions or strategies, "honest" ($i = 1$) and "cheat" ($i = 2$); and each buyer also has two alternative strategies, "inspect" ($i = 1$) and "don't inspect" ($i = 2$). Since the strategy/state simplices here are 1-dimensional the state $s = ((s_1^1, s_2^1), (s_1^2, s_2^2))$ can be described by a point (p, q) in the square $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$, with $s_1^1 = p$ as the fraction of buyers who inspect and $s_1^2 = q$ as the fraction of honest sellers, so $s_2^1 = 1 - p$ and $s_2^2 = 1 - q$.

As for dynamics, it is assumed with Malthus that the growth rate of a strategy is proportional to or (with an appropriate choice of time scale) equal to its relative fitness and produced the following dynamic system

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{p} &= p(1-p)(1-2q) \\ \dot{q} &= q(1-q)(2p-1) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

It is shown that the system (1) of coupled differential equations has five fixed points (i.e., steady-states), at the center and at the four corners of the $p - q$ square and all other points are on periodic trajectories circling counterclockwise [1].

We produce a discrete dynamical systems for model considered by Friedman.

The discrete time dynamical system corresponding to (1) is defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} p' &= p(2-p-2q+2pq) \\ q' &= q(2p+q-2pq) \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

It is proven the following statement.

Theorem 1 The non-linear dynamical system (2) is the regular transformation.

The new discrete model of interaction between two populations

In this section we present new discrete model of interaction between two populations. Let $\Omega_s = \{(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)\}$ and $\Omega_b = \{(\sigma_3, \sigma_4)\}$, where σ_1 is the honest seller, σ_2 is cheat seller, σ_3 is the inspecting buyer and σ_4 is the non-inspecting buyer. For brevity assume 1 denote honest seller, 2-cheat seller, 3-inspecting buyer and 4- non-inspecting buyer. On the set $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ we consider the set of all probability measures

$$S(\Omega) = \{(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) \in R^4 : \text{for any } i \ x_i \geq 0, \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^4 x_i = 1\},$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the fraction of honest and cheat sellers respectively; and x_3 and x_4 are the fraction of buyers who inspect and don't inspect respectively. Since Ω consists of 4 elements, the set $S(\Omega)$ coincides with 3-dimensional simplex S^3 .

Assume that $p_{13,1}$ is the probability that after interaction honest seller and inspecting buyer the next moment of time selected seller will be honest. Similarly one can define $p_{13,k}, p_{14,k}, p_{23,k}$ and $p_{24,k}$ for $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$, where $p_{ij,1} + p_{ij,2} = 1$ and $p_{ij,3} + p_{ij,4} = 1$. Let us define a hyper-simplex $S_H(\Omega)$ as follows:

$$S_H(\Omega) = \{(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) \in S^3 : x_1 + x_2 = x_3 + x_4 = 0.5\}$$

that is the fraction of sellers is equal to fraction of buyers in total population.

As shown in [2] one can define the dynamic on hyper-simplex $V : S_H(\Omega) \rightarrow S_H(\Omega)$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} x'_1 &= 2p_{13,1}x_1x_3 + 2p_{14,1}x_1x_4 + 2p_{23,1}x_2x_3 + 2p_{24,1}x_2x_4 \\ x'_2 &= 2p_{13,2}x_1x_3 + 2p_{14,2}x_1x_4 + 2p_{23,2}x_2x_3 + 2p_{24,2}x_2x_4 \\ x'_3 &= 2p_{13,3}x_1x_3 + 2p_{14,3}x_1x_4 + 2p_{23,3}x_2x_3 + 2p_{24,3}x_2x_4 \\ x'_4 &= 2p_{13,4}x_1x_3 + 2p_{14,4}x_1x_4 + 2p_{23,4}x_2x_3 + 2p_{24,4}x_2x_4. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Examples

Example 1. Assume

$$\begin{array}{cccc} p_{13,1} = 1 & p_{14,1} = 1 & p_{23,1} = 1 & p_{24,1} = 0 \\ p_{13,2} = 0 & p_{14,2} = 0 & p_{23,2} = 0 & p_{24,2} = 1 \\ p_{13,3} = 1 & p_{14,3} = 0 & p_{23,3} = 1 & p_{24,3} = 1 \\ p_{13,4} = 0 & p_{14,4} = 1 & p_{23,4} = 0 & p_{24,4} = 0 \end{array}$$

For this model in long run all sellers are honest and all buyers don't inspect, i.e. in long run we will have ideal society.

Example 2. Assume

$$\begin{array}{cccc} p_{13,1} = 0 & p_{14,1} = 0 & p_{23,1} = 0 & p_{24,1} = 0 \\ p_{13,2} = 1 & p_{14,2} = 1 & p_{23,2} = 1 & p_{24,2} = 1 \\ p_{13,3} = 0 & p_{14,3} = 1 & p_{23,3} = 0 & p_{24,3} = 1 \\ p_{13,4} = 1 & p_{14,4} = 0 & p_{23,4} = 1 & p_{24,4} = 0 \end{array}$$

Then for this model all sellers are cheat and all buyers inspect, i.e. in long run we will have society without trust.

Example 3. Perturbations of first Example Assume

$$\begin{array}{cccc} p_{13,1} = 1 - \varepsilon & p_{14,1} = 1 - \varepsilon & p_{23,1} = 1 - \varepsilon & p_{24,1} = \varepsilon \\ p_{13,2} = \varepsilon & p_{14,2} = \varepsilon & p_{23,2} = \varepsilon & p_{24,2} = 1 - \varepsilon \\ p_{13,3} = 1 - \varepsilon & p_{14,3} = \varepsilon & p_{23,3} = 1 - \varepsilon & p_{24,3} = 1 - \varepsilon \\ p_{13,4} = \varepsilon & p_{14,4} = 1 - \varepsilon & p_{23,4} = \varepsilon & p_{24,4} = \varepsilon \end{array}$$

Then for this model in long run 77.5% of sellers be honest and 85.2% of buyers will not inspect.

Conclusion.

We can consider also a stylized interaction between two populations, called "officials" and "supplicants". Each official has available two possible actions or strategies, "not briber" ($i = 1$) and "bribe taker" ($i = 2$); and each supplicant also has two alternative strategies, "corrupter" ($i = 1$) and "not bribing" ($i = 2$). As shown in Example 3 rather very small perturbation of ideal model leads to very fast growing of corruption, since for $\varepsilon = 0.05$ one can see that 22.5% of officials will be bribe taker in long run.

References:

1. Friedman, D. Evolutionary Games in Economics. *Econometrica*, Vol.59, No.3, 1991, pp. 637-666.
2. Ganikhodjaev, N., Saburov, M., and Jamilov U. Mendelian and Non-Mendelian Quadratic Operators. *Applied Mathematics and Information Sciences*, Vol. 7, No. 5, 2013, pp.1721-1729.

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

Bosishga ruxsat etildi: 10.01.2026-yil.
Bichimi 70x100 1/16, "Times New Roman"
garniturada raqamli bosma usulida bosildi.
Shartli bosma tabog'i: 28,5. Adadi: 100.

"Noble Print" MChJ bosmaxonasida chop etildi.
100194, Toshkent shahri, Yunusobod-11, 62-uy.